

Complexes of Some Bivalent Meta^ls with 3-Acetylamino-2-Benzofurancarboxamide

A. C. HIREMATH*, M. B. HALLI and N. V. HUGGI

Department of Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga-585 106

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Complexes of 3-acetylamino-2-benzofurancarboxamide (L) with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) metals have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, ir and electronic spectra, magnetic moments and conductance measurements. The ligand field parameters, Dq , B , β and LFSE, are calculated for Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes. Polymeric octahedral structure may be proposed for the Cu(II), Ni(II) and Cd(II) complexes and monomeric octahedral structure for the Co(II) and Hg(II) complexes.

BENZOFURAN derivatives are well known as biologically and pharmacologically important compounds. There are potential sites in these derivatives for metal ions and there are reports of such metal complexes. In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the synthesis and structural features of the complexes of 3-acetylamino-2-benzofurancarboxamide with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) metal ions. 3-Acetylamino-2-benzofurancarboxamide is a potent nitrogen and oxygen donor ligand having five coordinating sites.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. The ligand was synthesized by the literature method².

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal complexes were prepared by treating the ligand in the least quantity aqueous ethanol with hot solution of metal chlorides in the same solvent, in 1 : 2 molar ratio.

In the case of Co(II), Ni(II) and Hg(II) complexes, the reaction mixture was refluxed for ~ 30-45 min and cooled. The complexes separated were filtered, washed 2-3 times with aqueous ethanol and dried in a desiccator over fused CaCl_2 . The Cu(II) and Cd(II) complexes were separated out from the reaction mixture as insoluble residues after heating for a few min on water bath. The complexes were filtered and washed with hot aqueous ethanol and dried over fused CaCl_2 .

All the complexes were analysed for metal and halogen by standard methods. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND CONDUCTANCE FOR Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Cd(II) AND Hg(II) COMPLEXES

Complex	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M (DMF) $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$ mole^{-1}
		Metal	Nitrogen	Chlorine		
CoL_2Cl_2	295	10.62 (10.41)	9.81 (9.89)	12.76 (12.55)	4.9	23.32
NiL_2Cl_2	300	10.26 (10.37)	10.01 (9.89)	12.65 (12.55)	3.4	20.02
CuL_2Cl_2	235	10.97 (11.13)	9.53 (9.81)	12.54 (12.44)	2.0	18.89
CdL_2Cl_2	300	18.34 (18.17)	9.24 (9.00)	11.33 (11.46)	—	21.99
HgL_2Cl_2	227	28.51 (28.35)	7.64 (7.81)	10.17 (10.04)	—	3.74

Physical measurements :

The molar conductance of the complexes was measured using Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge with a cell having cell constant of 1.0 cm^{-1} . The magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature, using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. The ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes were recorded in nujol mull in the ranges 4000-600 and 600-200 cm^{-1} on Perkin Elmer 297 and 599 spectrophotometers, respectively. The electronic spectra in nujol mull in the range 1500-300 nm and in DMF solution ($10^{-3} M$) in the range 900-340 nm were recorded on DMR-21 and Elico model CL-24 spectrophotometers, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Cu(II), Ni(II) and Cd(II) complexes are soluble in DMF and DMSO and insoluble in common organic solvents while Co(II) and Hg(II) complexes are soluble in common organic solvents. The molar

* Author for correspondence.

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENTS OF ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) AND CALCULATED VALUES OF LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Complex	State	Frequency cm ⁻¹	Transitions	Dq cm ⁻¹	B cm ⁻¹	β	β %	LFSE k.cal/mole	ν ₂ /ν ₁
CoL ₂ Cl ₂	Nujol (DMF)	ν ₁ : 8197	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	938	836	0.86	13.55	15.99	1.99
		ν ₂ : 16390 (15150, 16670 sh)	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g} (F)						
		ν ₃ : 19610 (19230, 33000)	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) C.T.						
NiL ₂ Cl ₂		ν ₁ : 7092	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F)	709	1013	0.96	4.7	24.31	1.66
		ν ₂ : 11764 (12820)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F)						
		ν ₃ : 24390 (25000, 30700)	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P) C.T.						
CuL ₂ Cl ₂		ν ₁ : } ν ₂ : } ν ₃ : }	² B _{1g} → ² A _{1g} ² B _{1g} → ² B _{2g} ² B _{1g} → ² E _g C.T.	1290	—	—	—	22.12	—
		12900 (13160)							
		28500							

conductance of all the complexes in DMF (10⁻³ M) fall in the 3-22 ohm⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹ range indicating that the complexes are non-electrolytes⁸. The small conductivity observed may be due to partial solvolysis.

Magnetic properties :

The magnetic moments of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes calculated from the corrected magnetic susceptibilities are given in Table 1. The observed magnetic moment 4.9 B.M. of the Co(II) complex is within the 4.7-5.2 B.M. range, reported⁴ for high spin octahedral complexes. The magnetic moment value 3.4 B.M. observed for Ni(II) is within the range expected (2.9-3.4 B.M.) for octahedral complexes⁴. The Cu(II) complex exhibits magnetic moment of the order of 2.0 B.M., which agrees well with the spin only value⁵. The Cd(II) and Hg(II) being d¹⁰ ions show diamagnetism.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes are listed in Table 2 along with their ligand field parameters such as Dq, B, β and LFSE. The electronic spectra of Co(II) complex shows three absorption bands at 8197, 16390 and 19610 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}→⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}→⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions⁹, respectively in distorted octahedral geometry around the metal ion. The ligand field parameters calculated from the band positions ν₁ and ν₃ by using Ballhausen equation⁷ are consistent with octahedral configuration of Co(II) complex. The ν₂/ν₁ ratio 1.99 is lower than the theoretical value 2.1-2.2 which supports the distorted octahedral geometry. The light pink coloured Co(II) complex in DMF shows bands at 15150 cm⁻¹ with shoulders at 16670 and 19230 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν₂ and ν₃, respectively and suggesting an octahedral geometry around Co(II) ion. This shows that the complex in solution does not change its geometry. The value

of Racah interelectronic repulsion parameter B (836 cm⁻¹) is less than the free ion value (967 cm⁻¹) suggesting a considerable covalent character of the bond. The spectral studies along with the colour (pink) and magnetic moment (4.9 B.M.) of the complex point out the distorted octahedral stereochemistry⁴.

The three bands observed at 7092, 11764 and 24390 cm⁻¹ for Ni(II) complex may be assigned to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g}(P) (ν₃) transitions, respectively in an octahedral geometry⁶. The ligand field parameters Dq, B, β and LFSE are calculated by using Drago equation⁸. The Racah parameter B (1013 cm⁻¹) is less than the free ion value (1040 cm⁻¹). The ν₃/ν₁ ratio calculated is within the range expected for an octahedral geometry. The solution (DMF) spectra of Ni(II) complex gives two bands at 12820 and 25000 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν₂ and ν₃, respectively in an octahedral geometry.

The Cu(II) complex shows a single broad asymmetric absorption band around 12900 cm⁻¹ in a distorted octahedral geometry. Duff *et al*⁹ suggested that the absorption band in the region 13000-14000 cm⁻¹ is due to a tetragonally distorted octahedral environment around Cu(II) ion. The studies on electronic spectra¹⁰ of Cu(II) complexes strongly indicate that the three transitions ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g} (ν₁), ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} (ν₂) and ²B_{1g}→²E_g (ν₃) are of similar energy and give rise to a single broad absorption envelop. In the present study, the broadness of the band may be due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The solution spectra of Cu(II) complex in DMF shows a broad band around 13160 cm⁻¹ suggesting an octahedral stereochemistry around the metal ion.

The intense bands observed around 33000, 30700 and 28500 cm⁻¹ in the case of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes may be assigned to L-M charge transfer bands, respectively.

Infrared spectra :

The ir spectrum of the ligand shows three medium to strong intense bands in the 3500-3175 cm^{-1} region, attributable to NH/NH_2 stretching vibrations. A medium intensity band at 3500 cm^{-1} is attributed to νNH vibration of acetyl amino group at 3-position of the benzofuran moiety. The other two medium broad bands at 3310 and 3175 cm^{-1} are assigned to νNH_2 vibration of primary amide group¹¹. According to Marcotrigiano¹², the coordination of amino group through nitrogen atom to the central metal ion should cause splitting of bands or shifting to lower frequency or decrease in their intensities. In the present complexes no such changes are observed and νNH band shifts to higher frequency side indicating non-involvement of NH/NH_2 group in coordination.

The higher frequency band observed at 1680 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is attributed to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ of acetyl amino group¹¹. In the case of Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes, this band remains unaltered and in Cu(II) , Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes it shifts to higher frequency side indicating the non-involvement of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ of acetyl amino group in coordination in all the complexes. However, the lower frequency band at 1620 cm^{-1} is assigned to amide I band ($\text{CO}-\text{NH}_2$) of the ligand, which shifts to lower frequency side with splitting and decrease in intensity in all the complexes. This is suggestive of coordination of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group through oxygen. The coordination of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ (primary amide) group is further supported by higher frequency shift of $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$ band in all the complexes by about 5-15 cm^{-1} .

The medium to strong intensity ligand bands in the 1115-1040 cm^{-1} region are assigned to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ (furan ring) vibrations¹³. The band at 1115 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum shows negative shift with splitting on complex formation in all the complexes. This suggests the coordination through the furan ring oxygen. This is further supported by the presence of $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ band around 550 cm^{-1} in all the complexes¹⁴.

The low frequency bands observed in the 480-430 and 290-230 cm^{-1} ranges in all the complexes but

not observed in the ligand spectrum are attributed to $\nu\text{M}-\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ vibrations, respectively¹⁵.

In view of the spectral measurements, high melting points and insolubility in common organic solvents of the Cu(II) , Ni(II) and Cd(II) complexes, we suggest polymeric octahedral structure for them, whereas a monomeric octahedral structure may be proposed for the Co(II) and Hg(II) complexes.

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